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MODERN CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN SHUSHA – THE CAPITAL OF ISLAMIC CULTURE

Abstract. The article deals with Azerbaijan’s greatest respect for religious traditions as a multicultural state, and declaration of Shusha by the Islamic states as the “cultural capital of the Islamic world” for 2024. It also deals with the huge reconstruction works carried out in Shusha, which was liberated from occupation, and the restoration of historical, cultural and religious monuments that were subjected to Armenian occupation with high taste, in the style of national architecture. It is stated that the restoration works carried out by the Heydar Aliyev Foundation in Shusha bring back the historical spirit of Shusha, and also include the restoration of cultural events and traditions that have not been implemented for years. It is concluded that the decrees signed on the declaration of Shusha as the cultural capital of Azerbaijan, as well as the declaration of 2022 as the “Year of Shusha” demonstrated to the whole world that Shusha is the historical and ancient land of Azerbaijan, that our people have centuries-old culture in these areas, and that our national and cultural heritage is based on deep roots.

Key words: Shusha, Heydar Aliyev Foundation, historical and cultural monuments, mosques, restoration works.

Introduction. Shusha, which is called the crown of Karabakh, is also considered the ancient cultural center of Azerbaijan, the cradle of our culture. Shusha has been one of the important centers of the historical, cultural, social and political life of Azerbaijan, the cradle of our country’s culture, the “conservatory of the Caucasus”. The territory of the city is rich in ancient monuments. As a result of Armenia’s policy of aggression against

Azerbaijan, Shusha was occupied on May 8, 1992, and historical and cultural monuments in the city were destroyed. The territories of Azerbaijan, including Shusha, which have been under the occupation of the Armenian armed forces for nearly 30 years, have subjected to great destruction, and a large number of historical, cultural and religious monuments of Azerbaijan have been damaged. As a multicultural state, Azerbaijan has always respected all religious traditions. Baku has repeatedly been the capital of summit meetings of world religious leaders. The destruction of our history, our culture, in short, our cultural heritage by Armenian aggressors during the occupation period showed Armenian vandalism and the inner face of Armenians to the world once again. There were about 170 religious, historical and cultural monuments in Shusha before the occupation. Historical monuments, cultural examples were looted, destroyed and ruined by the Armenian invaders. As a result of the aggression of the Armenian armed forces, 25 schools, 31 libraries, 17 clubs, 8 cultural houses, 4 technical schools, 2 institute branches, 7 kindergartens, 4 cinemas, 5 cultural and recreation parks, 2 sanatoriums, 2 hotels, a branch of the State Museum of Azerbaijan Carpet, Shusha State Drama Theater, Shusha Television, Factory of Eastern Musical Instrument, State Art Gallery, Children's Health School, etc. were looted, burned and destroyed in Shusha.

Shusha, the crown of Karabakh, not only impressed people with its charming nature, mysterious springs, great mountains, Jidir plain, "Kharibulbul", but also became an art temple that resonated with the whole world with its literature, music, and mugham art. Shusha has been rightly called the music conservatory of the East. Genius composer Uzeyir Hajibeyli, the founder of the professional music art of Azerbaijan and the author of the first opera of the East, Khan Shushinski, Seyid Shushinski, Bulbul, Niyazi Shusha were outstanding musicians who left indelible traces in our musical culture. Shusha was so famous for its mugham evenings that it became a rare place in the Caucasus in terms of musical culture. The Karabakh music school gave the world many well-known musicians in the 20th century. The music festivals and competitions held in Karabakh contributed to the emergence and development of new talents and created conditions for the recognition of the art of mugham in the world. An example of this is the All-Union Music Festival "Khari Bulbul" held in Shusha in 1987. The listeners were presented the recordings of 24 representatives of the Karabakh mugham school, which had a special role in the development

of the musical culture of our people, in the “Karabagh Khanandas” project of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation. These recordings belong to different years [6]. Today, the huge reconstruction works in our liberated territories, including the restoration and construction process in Shusha are carried out by the Azerbaijani state in accordance with the original architectural style of Shusha in order to restore the historical image of the city. The restoration of each of the historical monuments in Shusha is of special importance to us. President Ilham Aliyev signed a decree declaring Shusha the cultural capital of Azerbaijan on May 7, 2021, which once again showed that the city has a centuries-old rich culture.

The 12th Conference of Ministers of Culture in the Islamic World, held in Doha, the capital of Qatar on September 25, 2023, declared unanimously Shusha as “Cultural Capital of the Islamic World” for 2024. This decision is an expression of special attention to Shusha, which manifests the riches of Islamic culture. In order to nominate Shusha for the “Cultural Capital of the Islamic World”, the relevant mission of ISESCO was here and appreciated highly the construction works carried out in the city. Taking into account the restoration of the cultural heritage, cultural, historical and religious monuments of Shusha by the Heydar Aliyev Foundation under the leadership of the First Vice-President, ISESCO Goodwill Ambassador Mehriban Aliyeva, the Islamic countries declared Shusha unanimously as the “Cultural Capital of the Islamic World”. Today, Shusha hosts international events and large cultural projects [3].

The interpretation of the main material. The historical, cultural and religious monuments in Shusha that were subjected to Armenian brutality are restored with great taste, in the style of national architecture and returned to their former appearance. Most of the restoration work in Shusha, as in all regions liberated from occupation, is carried out by the Heydar Aliyev Foundation. First of all, the busts of our geniuses – Khurshudbanu Natavan, Uzeyir Hajibeyli, Bulbul, which were shot down by Armenians, were brought to their native lands. At the same time, the monument of Uzeyir Bey Hajibeyli, the author of the first opera in the East, the founder of our modern music, which was destroyed by the enemy, was erected again, and work was started on the restoration of the great composer’s destroyed house. It should be stated that a statue of the composer was erected in Shusha in 1985 on the occasion of Uzeyir Hajibeyli’s 100th anniversary. The house museum of the outstanding musician, our great

khananda Bulbul, and the house museum of the famous tar player Sadigjan have been restored. The Heydar Aliyev Foundation also carried out restoration works of the Mausoleum of M.P. Vagif, which was opened by the Great Leader, at its own expense. One of the buildings restored by the foundation is the Shirin su hammam, which reflects national architectural traditions. The hammam is on the list of nationally important immovable historical and cultural monuments and has been restored by preserving its historical appearance.

Today, the huge reconstruction works in our liberated territories, including the restoration and construction process in Shusha are carried out by the Azerbaijani state in accordance with the original architectural style of Shusha in order to restore the historical image of the city. The Heydar Aliyev Foundation carried out the repair and restoration works of Ashagi Govhar Agha, Yukhari Govhar Agha and Saatli mosques in Shusha. The architect of all three mosques was Karbalai Safikhan Karabaghi, and the mosques are on the list of important historical and cultural monuments of the country. The interior of the Yukhari Govhar Agha Mosque was destroyed, the decor of its minarets was damaged, and its covers were destroyed. Restoration works were carried out in the mosque after liberation from occupation. The stones of the mosque were changed according to the original project. The destroyed madrasah in the mosque area was also restored. Foreign experts also carried out assessment work on the Ashagi Govhar Agha Mosque, which was destroyed during the occupation, and the mosque was restored and returned to its former appearance. The historic Saatli Mosque, located in the Saatli district, was seriously damaged after the occupation of Shusha by Armenia. The Kazanchi Church, like all other historical and cultural monuments, is being restored currently. It is planned to restore the Kazanchi Church to its original artistic and aesthetic appearance. The Heydar Aliyev Foundation has started implementing another project in Shusha, liberated from occupation. Repair and restoration works of the Creativity Center, Painting and Carpet galleries were carried out in the city. The building in which the Shusha Creative Center is located, and which used to be known as the Caravanserai of Agha Gahraman Mirsiyab oglu, is on the list of nationally important historical architectural monuments. The Shusha Carpet Gallery is located in the building of the former Shusha Carpet Museum. The building was seriously damaged

during the occupation. Besides the repair and restoration works, the selection of works to be exhibited in all three buildings is underway currently. The works of Azerbaijani artists, works reflecting images of Karabakh before and after the occupation, as well as carpet exhibits will be placed in Shusha in a short time. Of course, this is not a complete list of monuments that have been restored. All the historical, cultural and religious monuments of Shusha will be restored and returned to their former appearance in the near future, and the city will successfully perform the mission of the cultural capital of Azerbaijan [4].

The Mehmandarov estate-complex, which is one of the important cultural and historical architectural monuments in Shusha, was also restored by the Heydar Aliyev Foundation. Specialists conducted assessment works in the estate complex, which was severely damaged during the occupation and was destroyed by Armenians, restoration works were carried out based on this, and the monument was returned to its former appearance. Today, Shusha hosts festivals, poetry days and many other important cultural events again. The “Kharibulbul” music festival, which was held with the support of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation on the famous Jidir Plain in 2021, Vagif poetry days, the final competition of the 8th mugham competition and other international events will heal the wounds inflicted by the enemy on Shusha and restore Shusha’s historical spirit. These projects include the restoration of administrative, historical and cultural monuments in the liberated territories, as well as the restoration of our cultural events and traditions, which have not been implemented in our historical lands for years. So, our lands liberated from occupation are currently being revived mentally and spiritually, besides restoration and construction works [1, pp. 169-170].

Large-scale restoration and repair works in Shusha attract the attention of foreign experts. Ray Bondi, the chairman of National Commission of Malta for UNESCO, a well-known expert on world heritage, published about this in the “Times of Malta” newspaper entitled “Shusha – the cultural capital in ruins”, said that Azerbaijan is determined to restore its cultural capital – Shusha. Shusha is a place of value, history, heritage, culture and natural beauty. Shusha must be preserved and passed on to future generations [5].

Conclusion. The Decrees on the declaration of Shusha as the cultural capital of Azerbaijan and the declaration of 2022 as the “Year of Shusha” are wise decisions that contain great goals and works considered for future success. Besides restoring former status and glory of Shusha, these signed decrees show

to the whole world that it is a historical and ancient land of Azerbaijan, that our people have centuries-old culture in these lands, and that our national-cultural and historical heritage is based on deep roots. “The declaration of 2022 as the “Year of Shusha” in Azerbaijan and the implementation of comprehensive measures related to the historical past, present and future of Shusha are of great importance. It is also a message to the whole world. The world will witness the huge projects implemented after the cultural capital of Azerbaijan was returned to its original owners [2, p. 21]. Our head of state stated during his visit to Shusha that this city will soon be restored: “I said that Shusha will become one of the most beautiful cities not only in Azerbaijan, but in the world, and we will achieve this”.

Construction works started in Shusha after liberation from occupation confirmed this once again. Yes, the Victorious Army of Azerbaijan liberated Karabakh from the invaders many years later. The 30-year conflict ended in 44 days with the rightful victory of Azerbaijan. Reconstruction works, socio and economic innovations, cultural development, creation of new infrastructure, living and business activities of our citizens who have returned to their native land are considered as the highest priority.

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İSLAM MƏDƏNİYYƏTİNİN PAYTAXTI ŞUŞADA MÜASİR MƏDƏNİ İNKİŞAF

Məqalədə Azərbaycanın multikultural dövlət kimi hər zaman dini ənənələrə hörmətlə yanaşmasından, İslam dövlətlərinin Şuşa şəhərini 2024-cü il üzrə “İslam dünyasının mədəniyyət paytaxtı” elan etməsindən bəhs olunur. Həmçinin işğaldan azad olunmuş Şuşa şəhərində həyata keçirilən nəhəng

yenidənqurma işlərindən, erməni işğalına məruz qalan tarixi, mədəni, dini abidələrin yüksək zövqlə, milli memarlıq üslubunda yenidən bərpa olunmasından bəhs olunur. Qeyd olunur ki, Şuşada Heydər Əliyev Fondu tərəfindən aparılan bərpa işləri Şuşanın tarixi ruhunu özünə qaytarır, həm də illərdir həyata keçirilməyən mədəni tədbirlərin, ənənələrimizin bərpasını əhatə edir. Belə nəticəyə gəlinir ki, Şuşanın həm Azərbaycanın mədəniyyət paytaxtı elan edilməsi, həm də 2022-ci ilin “Şuşa ili” elan edilməsi ilə bağlı imzalanmış sərəncamlar Şuşanın tarixi və əzəli Azərbaycan torpağı olduğunu, xalqımızın bu ərazilərdə çoxəsirlik mədəniyyətə sahib olduğunu, milli-mədəni irsimizin dərin köklərə əsaslandığını bütün dünyaya nümayiş etdirmiş oldu.

Açar sözlər: Şuşa, Heydər Əliyev Fondu, tarixi-mədəniyyət abidələri, məscidlər, bərpa işləri

Фергана Гусейнова (Азербайджан)

СОВРЕМЕННОЕ КУЛЬТУРНОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ В ШУШЕ – СТОЛИЦЕ ИСЛАМСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

В статье говорится о том, что Азербайджан как мультикультурное государство всегда с уважением относится к религиозным традициям, о том, что исламские государства объявили Шушу «Столицей культуры исламского мира» в 2024 году. Также речь идет о масштабной реконструкции, проведенной в освобожденном от оккупации городе Шуша, о восстановлении подвергшихся армянской оккупации исторических, культурных, религиозных памятников с высоким вкусом, в национальном архитектурном стиле. Отмечается, что реставрационные работы, проводимые в Шуше Фондом Гейдара Алиева, возвращают исторический дух Шуши, а также включают в себя восстановление культурных мероприятий, традиций, которые не осуществлялись годами. Делается вывод, что подписанные распоряжения об объявлении Шуши культурной столицей Азербайджана и объявлении 2022 года «Годом Шуши» продемонстрировали всему миру, что Шуша является исторической и исконно азербайджанской землей, что наш народ имеет многовековую культуру на этих территориях, что наше национально-культурное наследие имеет глубокие корни.

Ключевые слова: Шуша, Фонд Гейдара Алиева, историко-культурные памятники, мечети, реставрационные работы.